

EXPLORE: A Scalable Infrastructure for LHC Open Data Analysis and FAIR Data provisioning

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Abstract

EXPLORE is a research data infrastructure deployed at the **GoeGrid** Compute Resource Center, University of Göttingen, as part of the **PUNCH4NFDI** project [1], funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG). The project aims to establish **FAIR** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data management solutions and provide dynamically allocated compute resources for physics communities.

EXPLORE integrates up to 200 CPU cores on an **HTCondor Overlay Batch System (OBS)** [2]. A dedicated **login node** hosts both the Central Manager and the Submitter, coordinating job submissions. Compute resources are dynamically provided through virtual worker nodes with 8 CPU cores each, enabling flexible and efficient execution.

To optimize resource allocation in real-time, **EXPLORE** uses **COBaID** [3]/**TARDIS** [4], a modular provisioning framework. **COBaID** acts as a flexible decision-making layer for managing heterogeneous resources, while **TARDIS** enables real-time scaling of resources by launching or terminating worker nodes based on current demands. This ensures efficient utilization under varying loads.

The system employs containerized environments via **CVMFS** [5] and **Apptainer**, providing users with pre-configured operating systems and software tailored for LHC Open Data analysis. Real-time monitoring and performance tracking are handled using **Prometheus**, Node Exporter, and **Grafana** [6].

To support LHC Open Data analysis by a broad user base, including public and educational audiences, an independent login node has been deployed. While the PUNCH4NFDI ecosystem relies on a federated Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) based on **OpenID Connect (OIDC)** [7] and **Helmholtz AAI** [8], **EXPLORE** currently uses an interim email-based registration mechanism for user onboarding and SSH-key provisioning.

This lightweight access method has proven effective for early-stage user testing, particularly with high school students and non-institutional users. However, it does not yet align fully with the standard PUNCH AAI integration model.

Efforts are underway to align **EXPLORE** with the broader PUNCH AAI framework by enabling simplified identity onboarding and token-based authorization. **EXPLORE** may serve as a pilot for extending AAI usability to users beyond traditional institutional affiliations.

Public users can register at <https://punchlogin.goegrid.gwdg.de/> using a valid email.

Following an initial alpha phase, beta testing was conducted with high school students in High-Energy Physics (HEP) Masterclasses in Lower Saxony. These tests led to improvements in performance, accessibility, and usability. The infrastructure is now fully operational, supporting **researchers, educators, students, and HEP enthusiasts** in performing scalable and reproducible analysis of **CERN Open Data** [9].

EXPLORE promotes FAIR Science by ensuring the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability of CERN Open Data across a wide range of users. Through dynamic resource allocation, containerized environments, and open-access registration, the system fosters open, reproducible, and collaborative research. This approach ensures resources are accessible not only for the core PUNCH community but also for non-HEP researchers, educators, and newcomers to high-energy physics.

This paper presents the technical architecture of the deployed infrastructure, including integration with COBaID/TARDIS, access control mechanisms, and its operational impact since transitioning to production. Preliminary usage statistics, operational insights, and future directions for expanding interoperability and accessibility in research data infrastructure are also discussed.

Keywords: EXPLORE, LHC Open Data Analysis, Dynamic Resource Allocation, HTCondor, COBaID/TARDIS, containerization, Alpha and Beta Testing.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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